

FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE OF STUDENTS

¹Muminova Ranokhon Nabizhanovna, ²Sobirzhonov Sohijon

¹Kokand Pedagogical Institute, Associate Professor

²Kokand Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7605483>

Abstract. *The article provides information about the formation of ecological culture of students of higher educational institutions and that students should have a basic scientific system of knowledge about the ways of human impact on the biosphere, environmental protection skills.*

Keywords: *ecological culture, development of mental, spiritual, personal, cultural development of students.*

Higher education institutions form the main basis for the training of various specialists. During the years of independence, its effectiveness increased as a result of the fact that special attention was paid to the training of qualified specialists. The pedagogical programs of higher education have been revised. Modern teaching aids, educational and technical means have been developed. Special attention was paid to the mental, spiritual, physical, personal, and cultural development of students of higher educational institutions. Pedagogical conditions have been created for their spiritual, moral, ecological education on the basis of national and universal values.

Today's science of technological progress involves young people from primary school age in the acquisition of modern knowledge, requires scientific preparation for the correct visualization of the landscape. This is to increase their interest in the natural sciences, in order to achieve a solid mastery of the natural sciences, intellectual games based on the age-psychological characteristics of the widespread use of types, unique aspects of these methodological improvement is calculated from the actual tasks.

Three principles of sustainable development: Social development; Economic development; environmental development. Social, economic and environmental development by its integral nature forms the basis of sustainable development. Now, between society and nature in the era of scientific and technological progress of that time, relations are carried out on the basis of three principles of sustainable development coevolution which is a development in which the laws of nature are not violated, ecosystem stability is ensured, as a result of which every person lives in good conditions.

There are a number of factors that hinder sustainable development for many years associated with man, society and nature, and this has created differences between them. Such factors include: firstly, the completion of technocratic and social superiority over environmental developments; the fact that the human factor is placed on the second level, taking into account the ergonomic, psychophysiological and moral capabilities of a person not related to acquisition; co-evolutionary underdevelopment of ecology with economics, ecological violation of laws. The scientific worldview of readers is reduced to the study of biological laws "nature-man" understanding of the relationship "society" from the point of view of historical development. The concept of "scientific worldview" includes a variety of methods of teaching biology in different ways approached the sources.

Today we are witnessing the consequences of man's negative attitude towards nature. The natural balance has been disturbed due to the impact it has had on nature for many years. And today,

humanity and its future destiny require the solution of such issues. At the moment, efforts to introduce cost-effective, environmentally friendly technologies in solving environmental problems, consistent implementation of environmental measures or improvement of industry legislation are not enough to solve them. The elevation of the ecological culture of the population, a rational attitude to the environment, the formation of a sense of preserving the benefits of nature for future generations are among the main factors in preventing anthropogenic impacts. The importance of environmental education in this is also extremely great.

Over the years of independence, our country has created a full-fledged regulatory framework in the field of ecology, environmental protection and rational use of natural resources in all areas. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws "On Nature protection", "On education" and the National Training Program, as well as a number of other documents form the legal basis of the environmental education system. It should be noted that article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" strengthens the obligation to teach ecology in all types of educational institutions in order to achieve the goals of nature protection. It is obvious that it is important to improve the ecological culture of the population, especially the younger generation, in achieving environmental cleanliness and preventing environmental problems.

Chapter 6 of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 27.05.2019 No. 434 "On approval of the concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" provides for strengthening the content of relevant academic disciplines on ecology and environmental protection, it is also noted that the relevant academic disciplines in noecological areas include topics related to ecology and environmental protection, and are regularly updated on the basis of scientific achievements, new technologies and research in the field of ecology and environmental protection.

To this end, undergraduate students of Tashkent State University of Economics are taught such disciplines as "environmental management", "economics of the environment and natural resources" and "ecological tourism". The textbook of Gulora Bakhtiyarovna shonazarova "Environmental management" has also been published. "Environmental management" is one of the modern disciplines aimed at finding the optimal solution to topical environmental scientific and practical problems.

On the eve of the 90th anniversary of the university, a textbook by authors I.Khatamov, M.Sultanov, A.Yadgarov "Economics of the environment and natural resources" was published. This discipline is aimed at the correct understanding by students of the complex and rapidly changing features of economic and environmental life management in the context of globalization, training in the analysis of various information in this field, familiarization with the modern scientific and practical level of environmental management.

At the beginning of the XX century, the science of ecology was developing rapidly. Initially, the ecology of plants and animals was studied separately, later they were studied as a whole.

So, in the 1920s, scientists who were the first to study the nature of Central Asia created structures and a system of biocenoses, as well as the final model of biocenoses and landscapes. In the 1970s, the School of Ecology-Geography was founded for the first time, that is, the Central Asian School of Ecology is now M. The name of Ulugbek was formed at the Faculty of Biology and Soil Science of the National University of Uzbekistan. This school is still of great importance not only in the study of biocenoses and biotarcinial thickets of the country, but also in natural geography, which plays an important role, especially in the development of landscape science ideas. In addition, the merits of this school in creating innovations in the education of environmental

specialists are great. The progressive ideas that this school gave made a great contribution to the development of zoological ideas, both ecological and geographical in Central Asia, to the identification and study of the nature and natural resources of the country. Ecological and geographical works of geographical orientation were mainly aimed at studying the nature of Central Asia, its biocenoses, their origin, development and territorial division, zoning, creation of landscape maps. At the same time, methods of transformation of hot deserts and high mountains and their unique natural cenoses were developed. In the studies of Central Asian ecologists, in particular, the problems of studying the ecological state, structure, activity, dynamics and evolution of individual landscapes of this country, as well as the rational use of natural resources were developed. It is known that the peoples of Central Asia, including the Uzbek people, have long been endowed with the heritage of ecological culture. They were also analyzed by our great scientists of the past, Muhammad al-Khorezmi (787-847), Abu Rayhon Beruni (973-1048), Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), Zahriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530), who analyzed issues related to the interaction of nature, living organisms with the external environment. The essence of the method of ecological direction is that botanical scientists, together with the study of the composition of the flora, analyzed the plant as an organism, its relation to environmental features, soil type. Much attention in this process was paid to the study of the ecology of certain species of great importance for agriculture.

. The knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in all biological academic subjects, along with the generalization of competencies, the systematization of knowledge, the scientific world, it is advisable to solve such important tasks as the formation and development of vision in accordance. To develop the scientific worldview of students in teaching biology, independence of views, beliefs of students in various life situations, possessed features that prove the correctness of behavior and behavior, the study of general biological concepts in educational, practical and future professional activities, it is necessary to develop the need for application.

Meditation promotes the conscious and thorough assimilation of educational material by students, their scientific worldview, skills of independent and creative thinking prepares the ground for consolidation and development.

Ecological culture is a form of reaction to natural phenomena in the world as a product of holistic thoughts in the student's mind.[1]

REFERENCES

1. R.N Mo'minova, S Sobirjonov.INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876 2022/6/9
2. Шодмонова Ш.С. Формирование и развитие самостоятельного мышления у студентов высших учебных заведений (на примере профессионального образования): автореф. дис.... канд. пед. наук. - Ташкент, 2009. - 300 с.
3. Ходжаназаров У., Мухамеджанова Д.Экология и охрана природы.Ташкент.ТДПУ, 2016.
4. Muminova R. SCIENCES DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGY IN UZBEKISTAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876., Volume: 16 Issue: 06 in June 2022
6. Jumakulov, X. Q., and N. A. Makhmudova. "INDIVIDUAL RISK SOME ISSUES ABOUT THE MODEL." *Open Access Repository* 8.12 (2022): 554-560.

7. Jumakulov, X. Q., and N. A. Makhmudova. "SOLUTIONS OF SOME PROBLEMS ON RISK AND ITS INSURANCE OPPORTUNITIES IN ACTUARIAL MATHEMATICS." *Conferencea* (2022): 37-41.
8. Kodiralievich, Zhumakulov Khurshijon, Ergashev Akram Ahmadhuzhaevich, and Abdullaeva Kumushbib. "TEACHING THE SUBJECT" PROBABILITY THEORY" IN KSPI TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN." *Open Access Repository* 8.12 (2022): 262-267.
9. Ergashev, A. A., and H. Q. Jumakulov. "INNOVATIVE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES FORMATION OF STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS AND ABILITIES." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 162-168.
10. Usmonova, M., and M. Mo'Minova. "O'QUVCHILARNING BIOLOGIYA FANIDAN KREATIV FIKRLASH QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO PISA DASTURINING AHAMIYATI." *Science and innovation* 1.B7 (2022): 1254-1257.
11. Turdaliev, A., M. Usmonova, and R. Matholiqov. "ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ МЕТОДИК КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ МОЎХИЯТИ." *Science and innovation* 1.B6 (2022): 450-455.
12. MS, Usmanova, and N. M. Abdibannonjva. "Use of Modular Teaching Technology in Biology Education." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION* 1.5 (2022): 272-274.
13. Muydinovich, Rasulov Inom, Mamadjanova Svetlana Valentinovna, and Maxkamova Dilshoda Xabibjonqizi. "THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN METHODS IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION." *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education* 14.7 (2022).
14. IE, Ravshanova, Shermatova Yo S, and Meliboyev TT. "EMERGENCIES OF A SOCIAL COLOR." *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education* 14.7 (2022).
15. Meliboyev, T. T. "ENVIRONMENTAL EMERGENCIES THEIR CLASSIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION. Protection MAKING EVENTS." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429* 11.12 (2022): 212-219.
16. Usmonova, M., and M. Mo'Minova. "O'QUVCHILARNING BIOLOGIYA FANIDAN KREATIV FIKRLASH QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO PISA DASTURINING AHAMIYATI." *Science and innovation* 1.B7 (2022): 1254-1257.
17. Turdaliev, A., M. Usmonova, and R. Matholiqov. "ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ МЕТОДИК КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ МОЎХИЯТИ." *Science and innovation* 1.B6 (2022): 450-455.
18. MS, Usmanova, and N. M. Abdibannonjva. "Use of Modular Teaching Technology in Biology Education." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION* 1.5 (2022): 272-274.
19. Turdaliev, A., M. Usmonova, and R. Matholiqov. "THE ESSENCE OF THE TEACHER'S METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM." *Science and Innovation* 1.6 (2022): 450-455.
20. Alisherovna, Ergasheva Nazokat. "PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNITY AND ITS SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS." *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603* 11.11 (2022): 80-88.

21. Turg'unovich, Meliboyev Tavakkal. "ENVIRONMENTAL EMERGENCIES THEIR CLASSIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION. PROTECTION MEASURES." *Open Access Repository* 9.11 (2022): 301-305.